

PROSPECTS AND BARRIERS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the current state and prospects of digitalization of agriculture in Uzbekistan. In the context of global challenges such as climate change, water scarcity, and the need to increase productivity, the introduction of digital technologies is becoming a key factor in the sustainable development of the agro-industrial complex. The work examines state initiatives such as the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy, projects for the introduction of unmanned aerial vehicles, geographic information systems, and digital platforms for farmers. Particular attention is paid to educational programs and institutional support for digitalization. The main problems and limitations are also highlighted: weak infrastructure, high cost of digital solutions, and lack of qualified personnel. Based on the analysis, measures are proposed to accelerate the digital transformation of agriculture, including state support, the development of digital literacy, and the promotion of IT innovations.*

Keywords: *Digitization, agriculture, agro-industrial complex, Uzbekistan, information technology, artificial intelligence, drones, digital transformation, geoinformation systems, sustainable development.*

INTRODUCTION: The agricultural sector of Uzbekistan plays a key role in the country's economy, accounting for more than 20% of the gross domestic product (GDP) and providing employment for about 30% of the population. Traditionally, agriculture in Uzbekistan is associated with the cultivation of cotton, grain, vegetables and fruits.

The agricultural sector of Uzbekistan is characterized by high dependence on natural conditions, including the use of irrigation for most crops. The country's agriculture faces a number of key challenges, including:

- Low labor productivity.
- Inefficient use of water resources.
- High vulnerability to climate change.

However, given such global challenges as climate change, water scarcity and the need to improve production efficiency, the need to introduce digital technologies in the agricultural sector is becoming increasingly urgent. Digitalization can increase productivity, improve resilience to climate change and optimize management processes in agriculture. This article examines the current state of digitalization of the agricultural sector in Uzbekistan, analyzes key areas and problems in this process.

METHODS: The study used a comprehensive approach, including qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis. The main sources of information were regulatory and legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, official statistical data, reports of international organizations (FAO, World Bank), as well as publications in the scientific and business press.

Comparative analysis methods were used to assess the implementation of digital technologies in agriculture in Uzbekistan in comparison with international practice. In addition, a systematic approach was used to identify problems and formulate recommendations for increasing the effectiveness of digital transformation in agriculture.

RESULTS: In recent years, the state has been actively introducing digital technologies to address these issues. One of the most important steps was the creation of the “Digital Platform for Farmers of Uzbekistan” and the launch of a number of projects on the digitalization of agriculture. In 2020, a number of laws were adopted aimed at stimulating investment in the digitalization of agriculture, as well as creating a real-time monitoring and management system. On September 27, the UN FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), with the support of IT Park, launched the Digital Villages Camp educational program for young residents of the Fergana Valley in Uzbekistan. This program is part of a global initiative - the Digital Villages Initiative, organized by the UN FAO. The goal of the Digital Villages Initiative is to transform more than 1,000 rural communities around the world by connecting them to digital technologies to increase agricultural production, expand access to rural services and improve living conditions in rural areas. This innovative program aims to introduce participants to the Internet of Things (IoT) for smart agriculture through the educational process. Students will gain the necessary knowledge and experience in programming using open source solutions and assembling smart devices - sensors designed for greenhouses and household plots. Students will spend significant time in the field, where the devices created as part of the program will be thoroughly tested in real greenhouses and adapted to the unique needs of small farmers in the Fergana Valley. Participants will learn how to connect these devices to a Telegram bot, which will allow farmers to receive real-time notifications on their mobile devices and make informed decisions about timely watering or ventilation of the greenhouse.[1]

In order to improve the efficiency of using digital and geoinformation technologies in agriculture and water management, the Center for Digitalization of the Agro-Industrial Complex LLC was established under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main objectives of the center are:

- Implementation of digital technologies and development of software products in the agro-industrial complex;
- Creation of technological conditions for the implementation of "smart agriculture" technologies;
- Creation of a database on the agro-industrial complex and food;
- Implementation of geographic information systems in agriculture;
- Ensuring the smooth operation of software products developed by the center.[2]

Drone technologies play an important role in the digitalization of agriculture. Drones are used for aerial photography, crop analysis and plant quality monitoring. This can significantly increase the accuracy and speed of monitoring, which reduces labor costs and improves the quality of work.

A document regulating the use of UAVs is being developed in Uzbekistan. The document is being developed in order to create favorable conditions for the development of unmanned aviation, their effective use in sectors of the economy, as well as to ensure the safety of drone flights in the airspace. Taking into account the development of world experience, there is a pressing need to develop unmanned aircraft systems and the use of UAVs in the agricultural sector of the economy of Uzbekistan: monitoring crops, soil analysis, determining harvesting dates, irrigation

levels, calculating the vegetation index, plant condition and disease infestation, fertilizing, spraying pesticides and increasing the efficiency of irrigation.

Currently, in Uzbekistan, the area of agricultural and garden lands is more than 4.5 million hectares, and pasture lands are 20 million hectares. Accordingly, the potential market size of spraying drones in the country will be about 12.5 thousand units.

The use of UAV technologies and artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan can ensure GDP growth of 2-5% in the next 5 years, which will amount to 1.8-4.5 billion dollars.

Due to savings in time (3 times), water resources (up to 20%) and spraying equipment (pesticides by 60%), the elimination of crop damage by wheeled equipment (up to 5%), the accuracy of irrigation and sowing, the expected increase in crop yields when using drones will be: cotton and grain - up to 30%, fruits - up to 15%, rice - up to 25%, and also due to the processing of pastures, an increase in livestock production is expected up to 10%. [3] On December 28, 2022, a conference on the digitalization of the agricultural sector was held at the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Representatives of the agro-industrial complex took part in the conference. Several information systems and platforms that were developed within the framework of projects for the accelerated digitalization of the agricultural sector were presented.

By the decree of the head of state "On approval of the strategy" Digital Uzbekistan-2030 "and measures for its effective implementation", several dozen projects aimed at the development and optimization of the agro-industrial sector were developed. In order to quickly implement these tasks, our country is studying and applying advanced foreign experience and the best technical solutions, and enjoys the advisory and financial support of the European Union and the World Bank.

Today, many farmers and agronomists use and apply digital technologies in agriculture. They help to study the current state of the land, determine the favorable time for growing or harvesting, monitor, forecast the harvest, etc. Like other developing countries, Uzbekistan is also implementing various measures for the comprehensive development of the digital economy, and is also beginning to use the latest information and communication technologies in the agricultural sector.

In December 2020, the "Strategy for the Development of Information Technologies in Agriculture" and the "Action Plan for the Implementation of the Strategy for the Development of Information Technologies in Agriculture for the Period 2021-2023" were approved, which consists of four main areas:

- digitalization of agriculture;
- automation of management and control processes;
- support for projects to launch a business in the agricultural sector;
- water resources accounting.

The Department for the Development of Digital Technologies in the Agricultural Sector and the State Institution "Center for Digitalization of the Agro-Industrial Complex" have also been created, which deal with issues of accelerated development of digitalization in the agricultural sector, the use of digital solutions that help control and maintain food security, manage land and water resources, and introduce modern technologies and software products.

Uzbekistan has been tasked with the digital transformation of the country's agriculture, aimed at ensuring a technological breakthrough in the agro-industrial complex, strengthening food security, and the targeted use of water and land resources to achieve increased labor productivity

in agricultural enterprises.

In order to effectively and rationally use land and water resources in the agricultural sector, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 17, 2019 No. UP-5742 was issued. The tasks were set to introduce accurate land accounting, create a database on the current state of land, etc. To implement these tasks, a portal was created over the past year and a half. This portal began its work in November 2021. 24 million hectares of land have been digitized and an interactive map has been created. It is also planned to launch drone services so that farmers and entrepreneurs can take advantage of the new data. Using such technologies, entrepreneurs and farmers will be able to cut their costs almost in half.

The importance of digitalization for the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is confirmed by the following regulatory documents approved by the Government:

- Activities of the Action Strategy for Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Period 2017-2021, which identifies issues related to the widespread and effective implementation of the digital economy as priorities;
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 19, 2018 "On measures to further improve the sphere of information technology and communications";
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 2018 No. 3832 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan";
- Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030";
- Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to introduce advanced digital technologies in agriculture.

DISCUSSION: Despite the progress in digitalization, there are a number of problems and difficulties that farmers and authorities face in the process of implementing digital technologies:

- Lack of infrastructure - many rural areas still do not have a stable connection to the Internet and electricity supply, which limits the possibilities of using digital solutions.
- High cost of technology implementation - small and medium-sized farms face the problem of the high cost of digital solutions, which makes them difficult for a wide range of farmers.
- Lack of qualified personnel - a shortage of specialists trained to work with new technologies limits the possibilities of effectively using digital tools.
- Difficulties with adaptation to climate change - despite monitoring technologies, their capabilities in the face of climate change remain limited. [4]

Factors hindering the implementation of digital technologies in agricultural enterprises are:

- lack of material resources and insufficient funding;
- insufficient government support, a low level of the regulatory framework governing the process of introducing information technologies in agriculture;
- personnel restrictions;
- poorly developed infrastructure, etc. [5]

Uzbekistan is actively moving towards digitalization of the agricultural sector in order to increase its productivity, sustainability and competitiveness. The introduction of digitalization in the agriculture of Uzbekistan allows to significantly increase the efficiency of resource management, optimize the management of production processes and improve the quality of products. Digitalization of agriculture in Uzbekistan opens up great prospects, including increasing export potential, resilience to climate change and improving the well-being of the rural population. However, to realize these prospects, it is necessary to synchronize the efforts of the state, business

and the scientific community in the following areas:

- increasing the efficiency of crop cultivation;
- introduction of precision farming technologies in agro-industrial complexes (AIC);
- attracting investment projects and creating new jobs;
- sustainable development of agriculture;
- state support and subsidy packages.

CONCLUSION: In the context of rapid technological progress and global changes, the agricultural sector, as one of the most important sectors of the economy, is in need of deep modernization. One of the main drivers of this transformation is information technology, which is becoming an integral part of modern agriculture. As shown in this paper, digital solutions cover a wide range of tasks - from automation of production processes to improving the level of management decisions and analytics, thereby ensuring sustainability, efficiency and transparency of agricultural production.

World practice shows that countries that actively introduce IT in agriculture receive significant benefits: increased yields, reduced production costs, rational use of resources and increased environmental sustainability. The experience of the USA, Germany, the Netherlands, China and other countries shows that strategic integration of digital technologies in the agricultural sector is possible with the concerted efforts of the state, business and the scientific and educational community.

Particular attention in the work is paid to the analysis of the current state of digitalization of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan. Despite existing challenges - such as poor infrastructure, limited access to digital services in rural areas, lack of qualified personnel and high cost of technology - positive changes are observed in the country. National strategies are being implemented (Digital Uzbekistan - 2030), specialized platforms and systems are being created (for example, Agrosubsidy, CropAgro, Marketplace), a system of "smart" solutions and educational initiatives is being developed. All this indicates a high potential for digital transformation of the republic's agro-industrial complex. However, to realize this potential, systemic and consistent measures are needed. It is important to provide broadband Internet in rural areas, support farmers in acquiring and mastering digital solutions, stimulate the development of local software products adapted to the needs of Uzbek agriculture, and develop digital literacy among the rural population. State support, including subsidies, preferential loans and educational programs, plays a key role in accelerating this process. The prospects for introducing IT into the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan go far beyond increasing productivity. We are talking about creating a new model of agriculture - sustainable, innovative and competitive. This approach contributes not only to economic growth, but also to solving social problems: creating new jobs, improving the standard of living in rural areas, ensuring food security and mitigating the effects of climate change. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the digitalization of the agricultural economy is not just a technological trend, but a strategically necessary condition for its development. A comprehensive and targeted approach to the introduction of information technology in agriculture can give a new impetus to the development of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan, strengthen its position in the domestic and international markets and ensure a sustainable future for the country's rural areas.

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